

DIFABILITY MOVEMENT PROGRAM TO IMPROVE THE WELFARE IN MALANG CITY

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Abstract

According to data from the Binapenta 1.5 million diffables are unemployed in Indonesia. Lack of expertise, knowledge and employment information for diffables causes inequality of diffable workers with non-diffable workers and a lack of continued assistance and control of empowerment programs carried out by various agencies. Therefore, Metamorphose Home is a diffable movement program aimed at fostering readiness and increasing the productivity of diffable workers and providing employment information for diffables. This activity method is based on the development of ESQ and intellectual. Furthermore, there is also employment information for diffables through social media, media partners, and direct activity. The results of this activities: 1) increasing the knowledge and ability of the average participant by 53.46% 2) two diffables have experienced an increase in average income of Rp550.000 per month, and 3) five diffables have been received On The Job Training in UMKM Jagoan. To support the sustainability of the program, continued mentoring is carried out through inclusion.inc which aims to help re-branding products of diffablepreneur in Malang.

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 8 of 2016 concerning Persons with Disabilities explained that the Company must employ at least 1 person with disabilities. Meanwhile, many companies have not recruited optimally the disabled workforce. In fact, the disabled population in Indonesia is estimated to reach 12.15% or nearly 30 million people. According to Binapenta there are 1.5 million unemployed disabled people. In addition, information sharing on employment that receives diffable workers is uneven. So that more facilities are needed to access information on job vacancies available for people with disabilities as well as to increase the skills of diffables in order to get decent work. From these conditions and problems, the authors propose "Difability Movement Program to Improve Welfare and Equity Distribution of Disabled Workers in Malang City" as a solutive innovation to overcome the problem of disability disability with non disabled people in Malang City.

2. LITELATURE REVIEW

Studies that conducted by the International Labor Organization (2017) is about mapping study are the participation of people with disabilities in the labor market still low, namely 56.72%

people with mild disabilities and serious disabilities on numbers 20.27%. Meanwhile, the difference of people with disabilities and non-disabilities in labor market is significant namely on numbers 70.40%. The difficult of people with disabilities can be influenced by several factors, like institutional discrimination, physical environment, and social discrimination (Yeo & Moore, 2003). The employment sector of the most people with disabilities are in the major of agriculture, plantations, and fisheries. This is the opposite of non-disabled people where around 40.11% work as employees. Persons with disabilities to work as entrepreneurs with temporary or unpaid workers, and unpaid family workers.

4. OBJECTIVES

This study aims to find out the methods of Metamorphose Home on improving the productivity and creativity of people with disabilities, connecting diffables with labor market, and Metamorphose Home's method on providing the information for labor force of disabilities.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1 Preparation Phase

During the preparation phase a field survey was conducted to the disabled community (Social Circle, Deaf Roots, Formapi, Gerkatin, HWDI, FKD, Gecama, Fomi), UniversitasBrawijaya Disability Study and Service Center (PSLD UB), Jagoan UMKM, Social Service, Manpower Office, and companies or industries in Malang City. We are also looking for some speakers for the Matamorphose Home program. The preparation phase takes place on April 25-21 2018.

5.2 Program socialization

Open recruitment, All categories of disabled people are allowed to take part in the program, except for severe mental retardation. The socialization was carried out by collecting diffables from various communities and held at SAC FEB UB on May 5 2018 at 09.00-10.00 WIB. In addition to the delivery of program socialization, participants also filled out the registration form to find out the interest of the class to be chosen.

5.3 Program Implementation

The implementation of the Training and Education program aims to build Emotional and Spiritual Quotient (ESQ) participants. Training and Education consists of three development focuses, namely the participants' emotional, spiritual and intellectual development. In all Training and Education activities participants are required to fill out the pre-test and post-test questionnaires to determine the success rate of each program. Questionnaires were made using the Thurstone Scale which will be analyzed by the participants' development results before and after the activity.

5.4 Program Evaluation

Evaluate all activities to see success and improve program activities to improve program objectives

6. RESULT

6.1 Preparation Phase

At the preparation stage, the Difable Movement program works in collaboration with the Social Circle, Formapi (Student Concern Inclusion Forum), Gerkatin (Movement for Indonesian Deaf Welfare), HWDI (Indonesian Disabled Women Association), and Fomi (Forum Malang Inclusion) to continue actively supporting activities. Metamorphose Home. We also collaborate with Yanda Maria, a Sign Language Interpreter from PSLD UB. In

addition, we have collaborated with several MSMEs under the auspices of the UMKMJagoaan.

6.2 Program socialization

In the socialization stage, participants are expected to be able to understand the series of activities and the purpose of the Metamorphose Home. At this stage 82 forms have been collected online and offline.

6.2.1 Training and Education

Training and Education aims to build Emotional and Spiritual Quotient (ESQ) participants in Metamorphose Home. The success rate of this stage is measured by the development of participants before and after the activity

6.2.1.1 Emotional Development

In emotional development activities, there is an increase in the desire of participants to become better individuals (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Level of Participant's Desire to Become a Better Person

There was an average change of 17.31% in the desire of participants to become better individuals before and after the activity. The level of desire to change the average condition at first was 7.78, now it has changed to 9.26 with an average change rate of 1.48. The level of desire to become a better person on average initially at 9.04 has now changed to 10.47 with an average change rate of 1.43.

6.2.1.2 Spiritual Development

In spiritual development activities, there is an increase in the desire of participants to do good (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Level of Desire to Do Good

There was an average change of 6.78% at the time before and after the activity. The level of desire to do good on average initially at 9.60 has now changed to 10.26 with an average change rate of 0.66

6.2.1.3 Intellectual

Intellectual development consists of seven classes, namely photography classes, baking classes, painting from masking tape, critical thinking, entrepreneurship, and handicraft. The existence of intellectual development is expected to be a provision for participants in the world of work. In critical thinking classes, there is an increase in interest in criticizing things around and the desire to contribute to the problem solving around the participants.

Figure 3. Participants' Level of Interest in Criticizing the Neighborhood Environment and the Desire to Contribute to the Mitigation of Existing Problems

There was an average change of 30.86% in participants' interest in criticizing and contributing to the problem solving around them. The average level of desire to criticize things around at the beginning of 5 has now changed to 6.3 with an average change rate of 1.3. The level of desire to contribute to overcoming the problems around the average initially at 6.30 has now changed to 9.05 with an average change rate of 2.75. In the entrepreneurship class, there is an increase in

participants' knowledge about digital marketing, how to increase product reach, ability to use social media and marketplace, and the ability to promote products.

Figure 4. Level of Knowledge and Ability of Participants Regarding Digital Marketing

There is an average change of 71.73% in participants' skills and knowledge about digital marketing, how to increase product reach, the ability to use social media and marketplace, and the ability to independently promote products. The average level of knowledge about digital marketing at the beginning of 3.80 has now changed to 6.70 with an average change rate of 2.90. The average level of ability in using social media and E-commerce at the beginning of 5.25 has now changed to 7.05 with an average change rate of 1.80. The average level of ability to promote products through social media and E-Commerce at the beginning of 4.00 has now changed to 6.60 with an average change rate of 2.60. The average level of knowledge about how to increase product coverage through digital marketing at first by 3.35 has now changed to 6.60 with an average change rate of 3.25. In the entrepreneurship class, we succeeded in increasing Pak Aji's (deaf) income by Rp.600,000 through his pastry business, delivering SitiNurLatifah (Tuli) to become a freelance model, and delivering five participants to become apprentice staff at Jagoan's UMKM. In the photography class, there is an increase in participants' ability to adjust the focus of the camera, diaphragm, ISO, and shutter speed.

Figure 5. Level of Ability of Participants in Adjusting the Diaphragm, Focusing the Camera, Shutter Speed, and ISO.

There is an average change of 69.13% in the skills and knowledge of participants in managing the camera exposure. The average ability level of how to adjust the diaphragm at first by 4.09 has now changed to 7.72 with an average change rate of 3.63. The average ability level of how to set focus initially at 4.63 has now changed to 7.54 with an average change rate of 2.91. The average ability level of how to set the shutter speed initially at 4.81 has now changed to 7.81 with an average change rate of 3.00. The average ability level of how to set ISO initially at 3.72 has now changed to 7.27 with an average change rate of 3.55. In the painting class, there was an increase in the ability of participants in how to paint using masking tape, making painting patterns, mixing techniques or color combinations, and bright dark law

Figure 6. Level of Knowledge of Participants Regarding Procedures for Painting Using Masking Tape, Color Mixing, Dark Light Law, and Ability to Make Painting Patterns

There was an average change of 130.09% in the participants' skills and knowledge in how to paint using masking tape, color mixing techniques, light dark law, and the ability to paint using masking tape. The average level of knowledge about how to paint using masking tape initially at 1.10 has now changed to 5.70 with an average change rate of 4.60. The average level of knowledge about mixing techniques or color combinations initially at 3.00 has now changed to 6.00 with an average change rate of 3.00. The average level of ability in making the painting pattern at first by 2.70 has now changed to 5.70 with an average change rate of 3.00. In the cooking class there is an increase in the ability of participants in making chocochip and nastar cakes.

Figure 7. Level of Participants' Ability to Make Nastar and Chocochip Cakes

There was an average increase of 74.09% in the participants' ability to make nastar and chocochip cakes. The average level of ability in making traditional cakes at 3.92 has now changed to 7.03 with an average change rate of 3.11. The average level of ability in making literary cakes initially at 4.39 has now changed to 7.42 with an average change rate of 3.03. In the handicraft class there is an increase in the ability of participants in making flower vases from newspaper rolls.

Figure 8. Competency Level of Participants in Making Crafts

There is an average increase of 28.39% in the ability of participants in making flower vases from newspaper rolls. The average level of ability in making flower vases from newspaper rolls at the beginning of 6.75 has now changed to 8.66 with an average change rate of 1.91.

7. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The diffable movement Program Team targeted a total of 20 participants with disabilities, but in the implementation participants who took part in the program reached 82 people with disabilities. During the three months of the activity, there were developments in the participants' abilities and knowledge. From an economic standpoint, Metamorphose Home succeeded in helping increase income from people with disabilities who had a pastry business of Rp.600,000 per month and delivered one person with disabilities to become a freelance model and four people with disabilities received an internship at the UMKM Jagoan. From this it can be concluded that this program can improve welfare both in terms of ability and financial independence of participants.

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